

Numerical Investigation on Thrust Generation of a Rotating Divergent Duct at Low Reynolds Number

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Abstract

In this paper, rotating divergent duct (RDD) was proposed as a bladeless thruster and numerical simulations were performed to investigate the thrust generation mechanism when subject to high rotating speed and low Reynolds number. Both the flow field and performance of RDD model were calculated when immersed in glycerin, it is shown that the static pressure of the inner surface is higher than that of the outer one and the velocity around the wall surfaces have backward component due to the viscous force and centrifugal effect of the vortex generated. Since the pressure difference is acted on the wall surfaces which are inclined, a small thrust force is then produced.

Keywords: divergent duct; bladeless thruster; viscous; centrifugal; low Reynolds number.

1. Introduction

Propeller works well mainly by inertia force at high Reynolds number and flagellum works specifically by viscous force at very low Reynolds number. However, when the effect of two forces mentioned above are close to each other, questions will be raised up whether the propeller or flagellum can work well with specified effects and efficiency. In addition, the propeller with protrusions can be entangled by debris easily and might be posing a threat to aquatic organisms in practice. In order to solve these problems, some new concepts of bladeless thruster have been proposed in public such as bionic fish tail and magnetic fluid propulsion system. However, the mechanical structure of the bionic fishtail is too complex^[1-3] and the magnetohydrodynamic propulsion puts forward high requirements on electromagnetic equipment^[4-6], therefore both of them are still under investigation. The studies on tapered shells under rotating mainly focus on the structural dynamics^[7-11] without flow physics involved. The boundary layer structure of the vortex in a nozzle^[12] has been reported, but the nozzle adopted is convergent and static with the fluid rotating inside only. To address the issues mentioned above, initially motivated by the forming vortices by viscosity and generating thrust by the centrifugal effect of vortex, a novel thruster with bladeless rotating divergent duct (RDD) similar to the side wall of a round table, as refer to Figure.1, was proposed in this study. CFD method was formulated to calculate the flow field and performance of a rotating divergent shell duct when immersed in the glycerin in order to understand the thrust generation mechanism. Compared with the conventional centrifugal pump^[13-15] (thruster), it is estimated that the structure of RDD will be simpler for eliminating several components like volute and blades.

2. Geometrical Model and Numerical Method

2.1 Geometrical Model

As shown in Figure.1, the geometrical model in this study is a rotating divergent duct (RDD) with inclined angle of 30° and thickness of 0.04 cm, the diameter at the frontal end is 2.0 cm and 4.0 cm at the rear end, the length of model is about 1.7 cm. The coordinate system is set to satisfy the right-hand rule, and the x-axis direction is the same as the flow direction.

Fig.1 The geometry of rotating divergent duct (RDD) model

2.2 Numerical Method

The calculation domain and the grid are shown in Figure.2 and Figure.3. For the computational domain, the far field is set to be a cylinder with a radius of 2m and a height of 4m. An unstructured grid is adopted, with a total amount of grid of $8e+6$. The wall surfaces are set as non-slip boundary condition. Rotation is applied by setting velocity at wall surfaces with a rotating speed of 14,400rpm, hence the tangential speed at the rear end is up to 30.2m/s. For the inlet boundary condition, the inlet velocity is set to be 0.001 m/s. The glycerin is specified as the fluid around the RDD model, with a density of about $1,260\text{kg/m}^3$ and a viscosity of about $1.5\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ at 293.15 K. The Reynolds number defined as equation (1) is estimated to be 1000,

$$Re = \rho v d / \mu. \quad (1)$$

where d and v denote the diameter and tangential velocity at the rear end, respectively. It is estimated that the RDD model experiences laminar flow. In our calculation, the double-precision mode and second-order upwind format are adopted for solving the Navier-Stokes equations for steady flow field.

Fig. 2 The calculation domain and grid

Fig.3 The grid around the model

The calculated thrust against the flow direction $T=8.8\text{ N}$ and the thrust coefficient $K_T=0.047$, where the thrust coefficient is defined as equation (2)

$$K_T = T / (\rho n^2 d^4). \quad (2)$$

The calculated moment $M=1.2 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}$ and moment coefficient $K_M=0.16$, where the moment coefficient is defined as equation (3)

$$K_M=M/(\rho n^2 d^5). \tag{3}$$

In order to double check the uncertainties probably produced by grid quality, another grid with the amount of grid of $2e+6$ is adopted for calculation with the solver settings unchanged, accordingly, the total thrust force and moment calculated are $T=8.2 \text{ N}$ and $M=1.2 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}$, respectively.

3. Results Analysis

The static pressure, total pressure, total vorticity and velocity components are used to describe the flow field around the RDD model in order to understand the thrust generation mechanism. The static pressure distribution on the wall surfaces and cross-sectional view are presented in Figure.4(a) and Figure.4(b), respectively, it is shown that the static pressure on the inner wall surface is significantly higher than that on the outer surface to provide the centripetal force which is needed for the fluid to rotate, as a result, the thrust force represented by the forward component can be generated due to the pressure difference acting on the wall surfaces which are inclined. Meanwhile, as r and x increase, the static pressure on the inner wall surface tends to be higher, while that on the outer surface becomes lower.

Fig.4 The static pressure contour

The total pressure contour representing the energy of fluid is illustrated in Figure.5. The increase of total pressure indicates that the wall is injecting energy into the fluid. From the vorticity contour as shown in Figure.6, it is found that the vorticity concentration area is very consistent with the high total pressure one, implying that the fluid starts to rotate due to the wall effects and the vortices are generated thereafter.

Fig. 5 The total pressure contour

Fig.6 The total vorticity contour

The centerline cross-sectional views of contour plots for velocity components at three different coordinate axes z , y , x are depicted in Figure.7, representing the tangential, radial and axial velocity of the fluid flow, respectively. As can be seen, there is an obvious high-speed concentrated area near the wall surface. It is observed that the fluid starts to rotate due to viscous force, producing

z -velocity. The y -velocity and x -velocity are produced due to centrifugal effect and limitation of the wall surfaces which are inclined. The backward component of velocity is produced by the backward component of normal force from the wall, which, according to Newton's third law, can in turn generate a forward thrust. A relative sharp growth on y -velocity is observed at the rear end of the wall, as shown in Figure.7(b), which means that the wall will no longer provide the centripetal force to the fluid, hence rapid outward centrifugal flow occurred.

Fig.7 Velocity component contours at centerline cross-section

Based on Figure.7, it is found that there is a narrow and strong influence area in vicinity of the wall surface caused by the viscosity. As x increasing, r and tangential velocity of the wall will also increase, implying that more normal force will act on the wall surface to provide centripetal force for the rotating fluid. When the fluid leaves the wall surface, its energy dissipates rapidly, which is consistent with the characteristics of low Reynolds number flows.

4. Concluding Remarks

Motivated by forming vortices by viscosity and generating thrust by the centrifugal effect of the vortices, this paper proposes a rotating divergent duct (RDD) subject to high rotating speed and low Reynolds number. By means of CFD, the flow field and performance of the model were calculated to understand the thrust generation mechanism. It is found that the model can generate a small thrust at low Reynolds number. Observation of the flow field shows that the vortices around the wall have backward velocity components and there exists a significant static pressure difference between the inner and outer surfaces, thus the thrust can be generated.

In the next step, the range of Reynolds number will be extended to get more characteristics of RDD. Analytical solution and experiments are also needed to be carried out as comparisons with the numerical data. Furthermore, the model can be improved in many aspects, such as by placing multi-layer co-axial rotors to improve space utilization rate and adding extension segment as stator following the rotor to recover the kinetic energy of vortices. In addition, even if the rotating duct is a side wall of cylinder which is symmetric, thrust may also be generated due to symmetry breaking.

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